

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS AND DIAGNOSTIC CRITERIA OF SEPSIS IN THE INTENSIVE CARE UNIT (ICU)

Mansurova H.T.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Senior Lecturer

Suleymanova T.H.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Biology, Senior Lecturer

Gasimova M.Ch.,

Assistant

Badalova A.T.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Novruzova M.S.,

Doctor of Philosophy in Biology, Associate Professor

Talibova J.Kh.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Senior Lecturer

Azerbaijan Medical University

Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology,

Department of Pathological Physiology

Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

The aim of our study was to identify etiological factors and resistant strains among them to prevent death from severe sepsis and septic shock in the modern era. Hemoculture was obtained from blood samples using a BACT/ALERT® 3D analyzer. Antibiotic resistance of bacteria was studied using the Kirby-Bauer disk diffusion method according to the instructions of the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) 77 (55.8±4.2) Gram (-), 61 (44.2±6.2) Gram (+) bacteria were present. In our study, the synthesis of ESBL in RISK Klebsiella spp. In most cases, 15 (71%) and Escherichia coli 15 (75%) strains were identified. 58% were found in S.aureus (MRSA) strains.

Keywords: sepsis, MRSA, E.coli, K.pneumoniae, ESBL

Sepsis is a life-threatening multi-organ dysfunction resulting from dysregulation of the body's immune response to infection and hemodynamic changes. It is a systemic infectious complication caused by various microorganisms (bacteria, viruses, fungi) and especially their toxins, which manifests itself with the same clinical symptoms regardless of the type of causative agent. It should be noted that during treatment, especially pathogens with antimicrobial resistance (AMR) cause clinical sepsis and septic shock, increasing the risk of death in the hospital. Sepsis can develop in any patient, but the elderly, newborns, pregnant or immunocompromised patients are at higher risk. Sepsis is a serious health problem with approximately 2.5 million neonatal deaths worldwide each year. Sepsis begins with the entry of microorganisms into the blood stream and spread throughout the body, multiplying in patients with immune deficiency. Microorganisms and their metabolites enter the systemic blood from the source of infection [1, 2, 3, 4].

In the pathogenesis of bacterial sepsis, pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) in microorganisms bind to receptors for antigen on the surface of antigen-presenting cells (APC) (eg, TLR) and other cell surface receptors. PAMPs are lipopolysaccharide (LPS), proteases and other cellular structures in Gram (-) bacteria. In Gram (+) bacteria, they are hemolysins, lipoteichoic acid, exotoxin, enterotoxins and peptidoglycan. LPS binds to the CD14/TLR4 complex on

the surface of APC, after a few minutes pro-inflammatory (PAF - platelet-activating factor, TNF- α , IL-1, IL-6) and anti-inflammatory IL-10 (inhibiting regulates the cellular immune response) is secreted. In sepsis, flagella bind to TLR 5 and cause organ damage in the lung, liver and heart, and with LPS in the intestine and kidney. The function of these cytokines, which are secreted against bacteria and their products, is to protect against infection under normal conditions, but during sepsis the cellular responses become overactive and out of balance. As a result, excessive amounts of secreted cytokines cause extensive damage to endothelial cells, hemodynamic changes occur, and can even result in organ failure. In addition, the synthesis of prostaglandin and thromboxane as a result of the direct effect of cytokines or endotoxin can cause increased capillary permeability and stagnation of blood in the microcirculation. TNF- α (by increasing NO synthesis) is the first cytokine synthesized during inflammation. Its high secretion can cause shock by causing peripheral vasodilatation. TNF- α and IL-1 convert fibrinogen to fibrin by increasing the synthesis of tissue factor thrombin, a key component of intravascular coagulation. Intravascular coagulation (ICT), which occurs in 50% of sepsis cases and causes multiorgan failure, occurs by this mechanism. Endotoxin and lipoteichoic acid also activate the complement system. The C3a and C5a components of complement induce the release of vasoactive sub-

stances such as histamine, which can cause hypotension. An imbalance between these mechanisms can result in severe tissue damage, immunosuppression and secondary infections in the body. In patients with septic shock, an increase in aminotransferase, thrombocytopenia, ICT, critical weakening of tissue perfusion, and acute failure of many organs, including lungs, kidneys, and liver, may occur [5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

In 3 studies, serum concentrations of TNF- α and interleukin-6 during sepsis were reported. The concentration of TNF- α was higher in Gram (-) bacteria than in Gram (+). There was no significant difference in the concentration of Il-6 between the two groups [11].

To diagnose Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) during sepsis, from the following: temperature $>38.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ or $<36.0^{\circ}\text{C}$, pulse rate - tachycardia $> 90/\text{minute}$, respiratory rate (tachypnea $>20/\text{minute}$ or $\text{pCO}_2 <32/\text{mmHg}$), leukocyte count ($>12,000/\text{mm}^3$ or $<4,000/\text{mm}^3$) must have a change in at least two. In septic shock, there should be atrial hypotension despite organ dysfunction and infusion therapy. Organ dysfunction - Sequential Organ Failure Assessment (SOFA) the presence of two of the three SOFA scale criteria is sufficient to confirm sepsis. The compensatory pro-inflammatory response (Bone 1996) is an immune defense process that prevents permanent damage to the body against the SIRS response. [12, 13, 14].

Sepsis in patients treated in intensive care units (ICUs) is considered a healthcare-associated infection (HAI). Timely treatment of sepsis can save the patient's life. In order to take the necessary treatment measures, it is important to determine biomarkers as well as symptoms. On the other hand, adequate empiric antibacterial treatment of the infection is impossible without knowing the causative agents and their level of resistance.

The aim of the study. The causative agent of sepsis was identified and resistance to antibiotics was determined among the patients treated at ICU.

Materials and methods of research. Blood samples of 300 patients who were diagnosed with clinical sepsis treated inpatient at the Central Military Clinical Hospital (RCHC) were examined.

During the examination, the patient's breathing, blood pressure, heart rate and skin condition are checked. Measurement of temperature and blood oxygen content is required. If the patient is conscious, the doctor collects anamnesis.

A general examination of the blood determines the number of leukocytes and platelets. It is important to assess the level of C-reactive protein (CRP), which is an indicator of the inflammatory process, by biochemical analysis of the biomarkers produced during the host body's response to the pathogen for the severity of the disease, prognosis and the effect of treatment. In addition, the amount of creatinine and bilirubin is analyzed. Specific markers such as presepsin, procalcitonin

(PCT) and lactate (lactic acid – high levels indicate improper use of oxygen by cells) should be determined regularly. Along with these, many biomarkers that have a role in sepsis and will help diagnosis and treatment: complement, cytokines, chemokines, DAMP, E-selectin are detected [15].

Bacteriological method. It is aimed at identifying the pathogen, choosing antibiotics and monitoring the effectiveness of therapy. To obtain hemoculture, 8-10 ml of blood taken before antibacterial treatment was cultured in 50-100 ml of liquid nutrient medium and incubated in a thermostat at 35°C under aerobic and anaerobic conditions. A small amount of broth was taken aseptically with a syringe when the microorganism was growing in the vial. Smear was prepared, stained by Gram method and subjected to microscopy. Depending on the type of microorganism detected, cultivation was carried out in suitable nutrient media. At the same time, hemoculture was obtained from the blood samples on the BACT/ALERT® 3D analyzer. The pathogens were identified by the API® system and resistance to antibiotics was studied. Antibiotic susceptibility of the strains was interpreted according to the European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST) criteria [16, 17].

ESBL synthesis of clinical isolates was determined based on the expansion of the inhibition zones of β -lactam antibiotics on the amoxicillin/clavulanic acid disk side by the double disk-diffusion method. Detection of carbapenemases was carried out by polymerase chain reaction PCR.

In the diagnosis of sepsis, in addition to determining etiological factors (culture, tests), useful diagnostic tests (CBC, clinical chemistry, and arterial blood gas) are also performed in the assessment of SIRS and organ dysfunction. These tests include complete blood count (CBC), urinalysis, liver and kidney function tests, ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) [18].

Results. Various bacteria were found in the blood of 138 patients. 77 (55.8 ± 4.2) Gram (-), 61 (44.2 ± 6.2) Gram (+) of bacteria were isolated from the blood of patients diagnosed with clinical sepsis. Patients included 24 (17%) patients with central venous catheterization (CVD), 32 (23%) patients with ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP), 34 (25%) patients with urinary tract infections, and 27 (25%) patients with surgical infections. 20% people, oncological diseases made up 21 (15%) people.

Table 1 shows the etiological composition of sepsis that occurred after various pathologies among the patients in ICU. As can be seen from Table 1, the most common pathogens in patients diagnosed with sepsis were *Staphylococcus aureus* (n=24; 17%), *Pseudomonas spp.* (n=23; 17%), CoNS (n=21; 15%), *E.coli* belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family (n=20; 15%), *Klebsiella spp.* (n=20; 15%); *Enterococcus spp.* (n=16; 12%), *A.baumannii* (n=14; 10%).

Table 1

Various pathologies resulting with sepsis	Etiological composition of sepsis after various pathologies among patients in ICU														
	Number of microorganisms	Isolated bacteria													
		Gram positive bacteria % ±						Gram negative bacteria % ±							
		<i>S.aureus</i>		<i>CoNS</i>		<i>Enterococcus spp.</i>		<i>E.coli</i>		<i>Klebsiella spp.</i>		<i>P.aeruginosa</i>		<i>Acinetobacter</i>	
N	% ±	N	% ±	N	% ±	N	% ±	N	% ±	N	% ±	N	% ±		
Central venous catheterization (CVD)	24 (17%)	6	4±2,4	4	3±1,4	2	1±0,8	3	2±1,1	3	2±1,4	3	2±1,1	3	2±1,0
Ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP)	32 (23%)	6	4±2,7	5	3±0,2	-	-	4	2±1,4	7	5±1,7	6	4±1,6	4	2±1,4
Urinary tract infections	34 (25%)	4	3±1,4	5	3±0,2	7	5±1,8	6	4±1,6	4	4±1,3	5	2±1,4	3	2±1,1
Surgical infections	27 (20%)	5	4±1,7	4	4±1,1	3	2±1,4	4	2±1,3	3	2±1,5	5	4±1,7	3	2±1,4
Oncological diseases	21 (15%)	3	2±1,2	3	3±1,2	4	3±1,2	3	2±1,1	3	2±1,1	4	3±2,1	1	1±0,7
Total number	138 (100%)	24	17±3	21	15±3	16	12±3	20	15±3	20	15±3	23	17±3	14	10±2

The frequency of detection of pathogens has changed depending on the localization of the pathological process. Thus, among the Gram (+) bacteria in patients with CVD catheterization treated at RITS, *S. aureus* was the most common 6 (4%). CoNS 5 (3%) in patients with ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) and UTI (urinary tract infections); *Enterococcus spp.* in patients with UTI 7 (5%) were detected more. Among Gram-negative bacteria, *Klebsiella spp.* 7 (5%) and *P.aeruginosa* 6 (4%) were identified in most cases.

E.coli 20 (14.5%) was dominant as the causative agent of UTIs, and *Acinetobacter* 14 (10%) was dominant in VAP. The same number of *S.aureus* 5 (4%) and *P.aeruginosa* 5 (4%) were found in surgical infections. In oncological diseases *Enterococcus spp.* 4 (3%) and *P.aeruginosa* 4 (3%) were the most frequent bacteria.

The results of antibiotic resistance of bacteria isolated from the blood of patients diagnosed with sepsis are given in table 2.

Table 2

Indicators of antibiotic resistance of bacteria detected from sepsis patients

Antibiotic	Isolated microorganism strains						
	<i>S.aureus</i> (n=24)	<i>E.coli</i> (n=20)	<i>Klebsiella</i> <i>spp.</i> (n=20)	<i>P.aeru- ginosa</i> (n=23)	<i>Acineto- bacter</i> (n=20)	<i>Enterococcus</i> <i>spp.</i> (n=14)	<i>CoNS</i> (n=21)
Imipenem	-	2 (10%)	3 (15%)	1 (4%)	2 (10%)	-	-
Cefepim	12 (50%)	4 (20%)	5 (25%)	5 (20%)	4 (20%)	3 (20%)	3 (14%)
Ceftazidime	24 (100%)	3 (15%)	10 (50%)	4 (18%)	3(15%)	13 (90%)	19 (90%)
Cefoperazone/ /sulbactam	2 (8%)	4 (20%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	5 (25%)	6 (45%)	3 (15%)
Ampicillin	4 (17%)	12 (60%)	16 (80%)	12 (52%)	8 (40%)	3 (20%)	4 (20%)
Amikacin	0%	5 (23%)	2 (12%)	1(4%)	2 (10%)	12 (88%)	2 (10%)
Linezolid	0%	-	-	--	--	0%	0%
Vancomycin	3 (12,5%)	-	--	--	--	2 (14%)	0%
Methicillin	14 (58%)	-	--	--	--	10 (72%)	2 (10%)
Ciprofloxacin	-	6 (30%)	2 (12%)	16 (70%)	6 (30%)	-	-
ESBL	-	14 (71%)	15 (75%)	8 (35%)	5 (25%)	--	--

As can be seen from the table, among Gram-positive bacteria, *S.aureus* has the most resistance to ceftazidime 24 (100), methicillin 14 (58), cefepime 12 (50), ampicillin 4 (17), vancomycin 3 (the least). 12.5% was detected. Resistance to linezolid and amikacin was not determined. In CoNS, ceftazidime 19 (90%), ampicillin 4 (20%), cefepime 3 (14%), cefoperazone//sulbactam 3(15%), amikacin 2 (10%), methicillin 2 (10%) were most resistant if it is not prescribed against linezolid and vancomycin. During the study of antibiotic resistance of Gram positive nosocomial strains, 58% of isolated methicillin resistance was found in *Staphylococcus aureus* strains (MRSA). These strains caused a decrease in the effectiveness of antibiotic treatment of severe patients diagnosed with sepsis. It should be noted that strains of these bacteria resistant to methicillin and vancomycin can be the etiological agent of serious life-threatening infections.

Among Gram-positive bacteria, *Enterococcus spp.* strains, ceftazidime 13 (90%), amikacin 12 (88%), methicillin 10 (72%), cefoperazone//sulbactam 6 (45%), cefepime 3 (20%), ampicillin 3 (20%), vancomycin 2 (14%) resistance was found in most cases. Resistance to linezolid has not been determined

Among the antibiotics in *E.coli* strains, ampicillin 12 (60%), ciprofloxacin 6 (30%), amikacin 5 (23%), cefepime and cefoperazone//sulbactam 4 (20%), ceftazidime 3 (15%), at least imipenem resistance was determined in 2 (10%) cases. 14 (71%) of *E.coli* strains synthesized ESBL.

Klebsiella spp. strains were resistant to ampicillin 16 (80%), ceftazidime 10 (50%), cefepime 5 (25%), imipenem 3 (15%), ciprofloxacin and amikacin 2 (12%) in the least cases. ESBL was assigned 15 (75%).

Resistance to ampicillin 12 (52%), cefepime 5 (20%), ceftazidime 4 (18%) was recorded in *P.aeruginosa* strains. In the least cases, resistance to amikacin and imipenem was detected in 1 (4%). *P.aeruginosa* ESBL was 5 (20%).

Acinetobacter spp. strains were most resistant to ampicillin 8 (40%), ciprofloxacin 6 (30%), cefepime 4 (20%), ceftazidime 3 (15%). The least cases of resistance were determined to amikacin and imipenem 2 (10%). *Acinetobacter spp.* ESBL was 5 (25%).

Discussion. The information about the etiological structure of blood cultures and their resistance to antibiotics in ICU is very important for carrying out antibacterial treatment during septic infections. In our study, the percentage of Gram (-) 55.8% bacteria isolated from the blood of 138 patients diagnosed with clinical sepsis was higher than Gram (+) 44.2% bacteria. Among the patients, the frequency of occurrence of urinary tract infections is the highest - 25%, others with ventilator-associated pneumonia - 23%, surgical infections - 20%, catheterization of central venous vessels (MVD) - 17%, oncological diseases - 15 % organized.

Among Gram-positive bacteria, the most common cause of sepsis was *S.aureus* in 17%, followed by *CoNS* in 15%. It was the most effective drug because none of the Gram (+) bacteria isolated from the patients showed

resistance to linezolid during the study period. The appointment of this drug in most cases results in the recovery of patients. Achieving positive results on the eve of treatment, in most cases, the onset of the effect quickly after the use of the drug, reduces the length of stay of patients in the hospital from 14 days to 9 days. Linezolid has a bacteriostatic effect.

ESBL was first reported in 1979 [19]. ESBL was detected in most *Klebsiella spp.* and *Escherichia coli* strains. It was later recorded in other *Enterobacteriaceae* [20]. In our study, the synthesis of ESBL in RISK by *Klebsiella spp.* 71% and *Escherichia coli* 75% were determined in most cases. Among the reasons why the indicated microorganisms cause severe clinical course of infection is the wide use of I-IV generation cephalosporins in clinical practice. 80% resistance to ampicillin was found in *Klebsiella spp.* strains in most cases.

The highest risk of inadequate empiric antibiotic therapy is usually observed in infections caused by Gram (-) bacteria characterized by multiple resistance to antibiotics [21]. In particular, the risk of mortality increases significantly, and typically exceeds 50%, for ICU infections caused by carbapenem-resistant bacteria. Currently, one of the most important tasks is the timely identification of strains of Gram negative bacteria that produce different carbapenemases and are resistant to carbapenems [22].

P.aeruginosa strains have shown resistance to most antimicrobial drugs, including carbapenems and imipenem. The reason for resistance to imipenem is explained by the ability of the tested strains to produce β -lactamase. Cefoperazone/sulbactam, the highest activity among cephalosporins against it, showed 10% resistance. *P.aeruginosa* showed 4% resistance to amikacin, a representative of aminoglycosides. Among the strains of this bacterium, the level of resistance to fluoroquinolones (ciprofloxacin), ampicillin, III and IV generation cephalosporins has gradually increased. One of the biggest problems in the treatment of sepsis has been the complications caused by *P.aeruginosa* strains, which have resistance to a large number of antibiotics [23, 24].

AMR strains from Gram-negative bacteria have become the dominant causative agent among the etiological factors of sepsis in ICU. Similar trends in the etiological structure of bacteremia were also noted by other authors. The incidence of *E.coli* and *K.pneumoniae* strains in the structure of bacteremia was approximately the same during the examination period. In those diagnosed with ventilator-associated pneumonia from Gram negative bacteria, *Klebsiella spp.* and *P.aeruginosa* were detected in most cases. *Enterococcus spp.* was detected in the most frequent cases in sepsis patients with UTIs.

Among Gram positive bacteria, *S.aureus*, CoNS and *Enterococcus spp.* ceftazidime, a third-generation cephalosporin, should not be used if it is found to be the etiological agent of sepsis. In *S.aureus* strains, 12.5% of *Enterococcus spp.* and 14% vancomycin resistance was determined. Since none of the Gram (+) bacteria recovered from the patients showed resistance to linezolid, it can be used in the treatment of septic infections caused by these bacteria.

In recent years, the increase in the level of antibiotic resistance of Gram (-) bacteria, which is dominant in hemoculture, is considered a serious problem in ICU. Most strains of *K.pneumoniae* are MDR. In the case of infections caused by these bacteria, carbapenems and inhibitor-protected cephalosporins can be used in monotherapy if there is a risk of resistant causative agent in ICU.

In most cases, antibiotic resistance to ampicillin and least often to imipenem was determined in *E.coli* synthesizing strains of ESBL. *Klebsiella spp.* ESBL strains were again determined to be resistant to ampicillin in most cases and to amikacin in least cases.

In MDR strains of *P.aeruginosa*, resistance was recorded mostly against ampicillin. Resistance to amikacin was detected in the least cases. Due to the clinical difficulties associated with *P.aeruginosa* infections and the failure of treatment, especially the high number of *P.aeruginosa* isolates that are resistant to antibiotics, it is one of the six pathogens that cause nosocomial infections worldwide (*ESKAPE pathogens* - *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Enterobacter spp.*) and is considered one of the most problematic bacteria to treat [25]. Isolates of *P.aeruginosa* showing resistance to the carbapenem class of antibiotics were evaluated as multidrug-resistant (MDR) (resistant to three or more antibiotics) bacteria [26]. Infections caused by MDR bacteria are particularly problematic, killing thousands of people worldwide every year.

Acinetobacter spp. in MDR strains, resistance was found mostly to ampicillin, and least often to amikacin and imipenem. Thus, in our study Gram (-) bacteria - *E.coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *P.aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter spp.* resistance to ampicillin occurred in most cases during the septic infection caused by besides, ceftazidime, cefepime, cefoperazone/sulbactam, I-IV generation cephalosporins from beta-lactam antibiotics; Resistance to ciprofloxacin from fluoroquinolones and amikacin from aminoglycosides was determined.

Treatment of sepsis requires immediate medical attention. This includes antibiotics, intravenous fluids, and careful monitoring. Healthcare-associated bacteremia and sepsis are often caused by pathogens that can cause rapid clinical deterioration in drug-resistant patients. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a major factor determining clinical failure during treatment, rapid evolution to sepsis and septic shock. After obtaining the result of the bacteriological study, the prognosis of rapid adjustment of antibacterial therapy is important for significant improvement or reduction of mortality [27]. In fact, sepsis is considered as a pathological condition that can be solved by mechanisms at the cellular level by studying the mechanisms of intracellular signal transmission. However, for the positive resolution of this difficult process, it should be noted that antimicrobial treatment directed against the etiological factor is also of great importance.

Conclusion. The only way to prevent the spread of AMR is to determine and identify resistant pathogenic strains. Modern diagnostic methods have the ability to analyze blood samples, obtain accurate results

from suspected sepsis patients, and provide all the necessary information in a short time to identify pathogens as well as AMR. The study of antibiotic resistance in bacteria is related to the fact that nosocomial infections are more often caused by these strains, causing complications and death.

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